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DIABETIC NEPHROPATHY IN CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS: FEATURES OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT

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***Annotation.** The history of the discovery of pathological changes in the kidneys in diabetes mellitus (DM) goes back more than a century. In 1840, in the Paris hospital, C. Bernard, conducting a pathomorphological study of a patient with newly diagnosed DM, recorded a sharp increase in the size of the kidneys [1]. Later works showed an increase in kidney size in experimental diabetes [2]. Thus, it was suggested that nephromegaly is due to a state of hyperglycemia [3]. Since the discovery of insulin by Banting and Best in 1921, "late" diabetic complications began to determine the prognosis of the disease. Currently, diabetic nephropathy (DN) is the most formidable complication of DM, occupies a leading position in the structure of the contingent of adult patients requiring hemo- and peritoneal dialysis [4]. For a long time, nephropathy was diagnosed at the stage when the symptom complex of nephrotic syndrome developed and chronic renal failure (CRF) was formed. Since the 80s of the last century, the possibilities of diagnostics and treatment of preclinical stages of DN in children and adolescents have appeared [5]. Currently, it is known that DN in "juvenile diabetes" is the main cause of disability and mortality of patients. Research results show that the older the age at which diabetes was diagnosed, the lower the cumulative incidence of terminal stage CRF [6, 7].*

***Keywords:** Diabetes mellitus, microalbuminuria, blood pressure.*

Introduction. According to the European Diabetes Association, in the population of children and adolescents with type 1 diabetes (DM1), the incidence of DN on the old continent is from 3.5 to 20% [8]. The fact of underdiagnosis of DN in pediatric practice due to the absence of clinical symptoms of the disease and the increase in the incidence of diabetes is alarming [4]. In childhood and adolescence, preclinical stages of DN are predominantly encountered, and therefore the main criteria for verifying this complication are laboratory parameters. However, in order to exclude/confirm DN, it is necessary to conduct a clinical and anamnestic examination of the patient, which

allows drawing the attention of the pediatric nephrologist to signs that directly or indirectly indicate the possibility of developing diabetic kidney disease. According to the hypothesis of B. Brenner et al., low body weight (BW) at birth can serve as a predictor of kidney disease both in patients with diabetes and in the general population. According to the authors, small kidney size can be accompanied by a decrease in the number of renal glomeruli and an increase in the pressure gradient in the kidneys [8]. This concept is not supported by the data obtained in the study of the relationship between weight, kidney size and the number of glomeruli. Also, population studies did not reveal a correlation between microalbuminuria (MAU), blood pressure (BP) and BW at birth [9]. Thus, it seems doubtful that pathologically low BW at birth can determine the development of nephropathy. The influence of this factor is possibly insignificant and does not play a role in the treatment of patients. Studies have proven a stable relationship between the duration of diabetes and the development of DN. The risk of developing and progressing DN depends on the age of the onset of diabetes. DN develops much more often and faster in patients with the onset of diabetes in puberty, reaching 44-45%, decreases with the onset of diabetes after 20 years to 30-35% and does not exceed several percent at the onset of the disease in adults [10, 11]. Similar trends were identified by a scientific group studying mortality in an international epidemiological study of diabetes [6]. From the moment diabetes is detected in a child, the degree of compensation of metabolic disorders, mainly hyperglycemia, mainly determines the potential risk of developing DN. Patients more often have unsatisfactory compensation of carbohydrate metabolism according to the level of glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c). The presence of other diabetic complications (retinopathy, neuropathy, etc.) may indirectly indicate a potential risk of developing DN in children and adolescents with diabetes mellitus [10]. DN is a complication of diabetes mellitus (ICD 10: N 08.3) and has a certain stage of development. In 2000, the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan approved a new classification of DN, which includes three stages of development of this complication: 1 - stage of microalbuminuria; 2 - stage of proteinuria with preserved filtration function of the kidneys; 3 - stage of chronic renal failure [4]. The advantage of this classification is its adaptability to practical diabetology and nephrology. In international nephrological practice, the classification of S.E. Mogensen is more often used, the main advantage of which is its focus on identifying early stages of DN. Since its development by the author in 1983, and subsequent additions, the classification has been of great interest to researchers of DN [12]. Given the need for earlier diagnosis of DN, the question arises at what stage the doctor has the opportunity to verify DN and begin therapeutic measures to contain the progression of DN. According to the classification of CE Mogensen, the development of DN is characterized by the following stages. I. The

stage of acute renal hypertrophy and hyperfunction is characterized by an increase in the glomerular filtration rate (GFR) by 20-50%, an increase in the size of the kidneys, and glomerular hypertrophy. Normoalbuminuria is typical (excluding the possibility of morphological examination of patients with diabetes. III. The stage of incipient DN, according to this classification, develops after 5 years of diabetes. It is characterized by MAU (from 30 to 300 mg / day), a gradual decrease in SCF. Some patients have a moderate increase in blood pressure. It has been established that from the moment of MAU onset, the blood pressure level increases by approximately 3% per year. Adequate insulin therapy allows stabilizing MAU and SCF. The appointment of complex pathogenetic therapy also helps to reduce MAU and prevents a decrease in SCF. According to the recommendations of the American Diabetes Association and the European Group for the Study of Diabetes, The study of MAU is included in the list of mandatory methods of examination of patients with diabetes mellitus types 1 and 2. Screening for MAU should be carried out as follows: once a year after 5 years from the onset of diabetes (at the onset of the underlying disease before the onset or after the end of the pubertal period) or 1-2 times a year from the moment of diagnosis of diabetes (at the onset during the pubertal period). In patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM2), MAU screening is recommended to be carried out once a year from the moment of diagnosis of diabetes [16]. The issue of early detection of DN, i.e., in the preclinical stages, is fundamentally important, since the possibility of slowing the development of DN and postponing the development of uremia has been proven. Currently, MAU is considered a laboratory criterion that allows with a high degree of reliability to identify the preclinical stage of DN. The diagnostic value is the value of albumin excretion in urine more than 30 mg / day. The development of effective and rapid express methods for determining albumin allows for mass screening of children and adolescents with diabetes. The introduction of the Mikal 1 and Mikal 2 tests into clinical practice has been successful; the Mikal 2 test has proven to be especially effective and easy to use in the clinic [12, 16]. IV. The stage of severe nephropathy is accompanied by macroalbuminuria (proteinuria), persistent increase in blood pressure, signs of incomplete or complete nephrotic syndrome, and a decrease in SCF [17]. Clinical nephropathy develops after 10–15 years of diabetes and is quite rare in adolescents. Arterial hypertension, which occurs secondarily as a result of diabetic kidney damage, usually in adult patients, with an average increase in blood pressure of 5 mm/year, becomes the most powerful factor in the progression of renal pathology, the strength of its damaging effect being many times greater than the influence of the metabolic factor (hyperglycemia and dyslipidemia). Progression of the stage slows down with compensation of metabolic disorders, pathogenetic therapy [2, 10]. V. Stage of uremia. Formation of terminal CRF in children and adolescents is practically impossible, since

its development occurs after 15-20 years of diabetes. If symptoms characteristic of the uremia stage (decrease in SCF to less than 10 ml/min, arterial hypertension, intoxication) are detected in a child with type 1 diabetes, other causes of CRF development in the child should be considered. To some extent, it can be considered optimistic that DN, unlike diabetic retinopathy, does not develop in all patients with diabetes. DN occurs in 35% of patients suffering from diabetes. The risk of developing DN is highest in patients with diabetes history of up to 15 years, then it tends to decrease [12, 18]. Currently, it is known that children and adolescents can develop type 2 diabetes [19]. Research data confirm that kidney damage in type 1 and type 2 diabetes mellitus are very similar. There are undoubtedly some peculiarities, primarily related to the underlying disease. Patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus are older and have a higher body weight. With type 2 diabetes mellitus, arterial hypertension with subsequent kidney damage occurs earlier. In advanced DN in type 1 diabetes, there is a clear correlation between blood pressure and a decrease in SCF. In type 1 diabetes, a correlation was also found between a decrease in SCF and glycemic control, but this situation is less clear in type 2 diabetes, since no correlation was found between a decrease in SCF and HbA1c [10, 20]. The stages of DN according to the CE Mogensen classification are certainly a guideline in the diagnosis of DN and the basis for further research. According to the classification, the MAU stage develops after 5 years of diabetes. However, in recent years, this opinion has been refuted. According to the EURODIAB study, which studied the incidence of DN in 26 different centers in Europe, a change in the duration of DN stages in modern conditions was shown. MAU was detected in 18% of patients with type 1 diabetes and a disease duration of less than 5 years [21]. As can be seen from the data presented above, the main attention in DN in children and adolescents is paid to an early laboratory sign, such as MAU, and therefore there is special interest in studying the state of the glomerular apparatus [22]. The presence of morphological changes in all parts of the nephron in the early stages of the disease determines the need to study the functions of the renal tubular apparatus not only in long-term disease, but also in the manifestation of type 1 diabetes in children and adolescents [18]. Diagnostic assessment of other renal function disorders, which are usually analyzed by nephrologists in nephropathy (reduced ability of the kidney to osmotic concentration and dilution of urine), recede into the background in the practice of a diabetologist clinician. There are several reasons, but one of them is that in DN, neither the Zimnitsky nor the Volhard test can be used. The presence of glucose in the urine makes it impossible to characterize the function by urine concentration due to the error in determining the relative density compared to samples that contain only electrolytes and urea [23]. According to published data, the issue of the kidney's response to antidiuretic hormone in diabetes mellitus is relevant [24, 25].

The study results revealed a tendency towards a decrease in the osmolality of night urine samples in adolescents with the longest duration of diabetes mellitus. In patients with incipient DN, the reabsorption of osmotically free water was lower than in patients at the onset of the disease and in adolescents with a history of diabetes mellitus without DN [26]. The studies have shown that an increase in the excretion of the lysosomal enzyme N-acetyl- β -D-glucominidase in urine is an early marker of renal tubular dysfunction in diabetes mellitus. In a number of studies, tubular damage often depends not so much on the quality of metabolic control as on the presence of ketosis [27]. Standard assessment of tubular disorders by the amount of β 2-microglobulin in urine has shown conflicting results in various studies [18, 28]. To verify DN, differential diagnostics with "non-diabetic" kidney pathology is necessary. Some alternative disease of the urinary system can be suspected in cases where the course of the pathology differs from the typical manifestations of DN [29]:

- manifestations of renal disease appeared before the development of diabetes;
- detection of MAU at the age of up to 10 years;
- early and/or rapid increase in non-selective proteinuria; development of nephrotic syndrome; rapid decrease in SCF;
- changes in urinary sediment that are not characteristic of DN (hematuria, leukocyturia, cylindruria, etc.);
- differential diagnosis should be considered in case of development of renal pathology against the background of constantly optimal compensation of diabetes (the level of HbA1c at times in very high concentrations glucose inhibits their growth. According to research, strains of Escherichia coli expressing fimbriae of the 1st type have higher adhesion to the uroepithelium in diabetes [29]. A significant reason for the high frequency of urinary tract infection is neuropathy of the bladder (a manifestation of diabetic autonomous polyneuropathy, clinically characterized by a decrease in urination, the disappearance of nocturia in a patient with diabetes). A feature of UTI in diabetes is an atypical (up to 90% of cases) asymptomatic or low-symptom course. Pathology can be suspected on the basis of unexplained decompensation of carbohydrate metabolism and the appearance of ketonuria in patients with diabetes mellitus 1. The principles of complex therapy of diabetic kidney damage consist of several boards. I. Compensation of carbohydrate metabolism. One of the criteria for optimal compensation is the HbA1c level of 7.6%, which helps prevent the development and significantly reduce the rate of progression of DN. Adequate insulin therapy for a child with diabetes mellitus should be prescribed by an endocrinologist-diabetologist. In Uzbekistan, only human genetically engineered insulins and insulin analogues are recommended for children and adolescents. The most widely used regimen at present is the intensified (or basal-bolus) regimen [10, 18]. Treatment with an insulin pump (CSII - continuous subcutaneous insulin infusion) is a more expensive method than traditional treatment with syringes or syringe pens. The use of a pump does not replace intensive insulin

therapy, but helps to improve it in order to bring carbohydrate metabolism control to target levels. It should be noted that self-monitoring, education of the child and parents in the Diabetes School are of great importance in maintaining satisfactory compensation of diabetes. II. Correction of intraglomerular hypertension is the most important component of the pathogenetic treatment of DN. For this purpose, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (ACEIs) are prescribed. According to the literature, timely and correct prescription of ACEIs can significantly reduce the rate of DN progression. It should be noted that ACEIs are recommended for continuous use at the proteinuria stage [4, 22]. Drugs of this group have become widely used in non-diabetic nephropathies [30]. In recent years, other groups of antihypertensive drugs have been increasingly mentioned in the literature, including angiotensin II receptor antagonists type 1, as means of correcting intraglomerular and systemic hypertension in DN. However, the use of these drugs in children is currently limited [31]. III. Clinical studies have demonstrated the advisability of using glycosaminoglycan preparations in the treatment of incipient DN; they have the ability to prevent mesangial proliferation and hyperproduction of the extracellular matrix, as well as thickening of the glomerular basement membrane and impairment of its permeability and charge selectivity [32]. IV. The issue of limiting animal protein in the treatment of DN in adolescents is currently under discussion. The purpose of such restrictions is to reduce the hemodynamic load on the kidneys caused by a high-protein diet and to reduce the filtration load of protein on the kidneys. Some authors believe that it is inappropriate to limit protein in children and adolescents as the main building material of a growing organism. The ISPAD Consensus recommendations (2000) propose using a diet with moderate protein restriction (up to 0.9–1.2 g/kg/day) in adolescents at the MAU stage, and at the proteinuria stage, protein restriction to 0.8–0.9 g/kg/day is necessary [33]. V. Hypolipidemic therapy (bile acid sequestrants, nicotinic acid and its derivatives, fibrates, HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors) is an important component of pathogenetic treatment in adult patients with DN at the stage of severe nephropathy combined with dyslipidemia. In pediatric practice, the use of the above drugs is not recommended due to the possibility of developing side effects [10]. In children and adolescents with DN, in case of detection of lipid disorders, the use of bile acid sequestrants (cholestyramine, cholestynol) is permissible. VI. The issue of correction of elevated homocysteine levels in children and adolescents using folic acid and B vitamins is considered as one of the promising areas of pathogenetic therapy for DN [34, 35]. VII. Treatment of concomitant pathology of the urinary system should be singled out as a separate component of therapy aimed at preventing glomerulosclerosis in diabetes mellitus. In conclusion, it should be additionally noted that timely diagnosis and treatment of DN in children and adolescents largely determine the quality of life and prognosis of a

patient with diabetes mellitus. Suppression of the rate of progression of diabetic kidney disease is most promising in the early stages. Subsequently, timely treatment and diagnostic measures can reduce the number of patients requiring replacement dialysis therapy and reduce the risk of cardiovascular pathology associated with chronic renal failure [4]. Currently, the issue of limiting animal protein in the treatment of DN in adolescents is being discussed. The purpose of such restrictions is to reduce the hemodynamic load on the kidneys caused by a high-protein diet and to reduce the filtration load of protein on the kidneys. Some authors believe that it is inappropriate to limit protein in children and adolescents as the main building material of a growing organism. The ISPAD Consensus recommendations (2000) propose using a diet with moderate protein restriction (up to 0.9–1.2 g/kg/day) for adolescents at the MAU stage, and at the proteinuria stage, protein restriction to 0.8–0.9 g/kg/day is necessary [33].

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